

The Constitution of Vasicine. Part I. A Synthesis of 2-Propyl-(isopropyl)-4-oxyquinazoline.

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In connection with certain investigations proceeding in this laboratory for a number of years it was found that urethanes condensed easily with acylamines in presence of phosphoric oxide and phosphorous trichloride to give substituted quinazolines (Cf. Sen and Rây, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1926, 129, 646). In the meantime, a paper appeared (*This Journal*, 1927, 4, 1) in which Ghosh claims that the active principle of *Adhatoda vasica* is represented by (I).

It seemed to the present authors that such a structure, apart from other considerations, does not seem to be very probable because the oxidation reaction on which it was mainly based is not entirely satisfactory. There is nothing very improbable intrinsically in an alkaloid having a quinazoline structure, as quite a few are known to belong to this class, *e.g.*, cytosine, thymine, etc. But they are of animal origin. But however, recently evodiamine, rutaecarpine (*cf.* Asahina, Manske and Robinson, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1927, 131, 1708) have been shown to fall under this group. Therefore, it was deemed that a direct comparison of the natural product with a compound synthesised, having the formula (I) depicted above, would place the matter beyond any reasonable doubt. The opportunity to do so arose now that the technique of Sen and Rây's quinazoline synthesis has been satisfactorily developed and we encountered no difficulty in condensing butyranilide and isobutyranilide with urethane in xylene

solution with phosphoric oxide as the condensing agent. The reaction took place thus :

The product was a monacid base and was purified by redissolution in acid and precipitation with alkali and then finally twice crystallising from boiling alcohol (charcoaled). The product from butyranilide, *i.e.*, where C_3H_7 is *n*-propyl, melted at 197° , whilst a specimen of the natural product, which we purified from a crude specimen kindly supplied by Messrs. Sen and Ghosh of Dehra Dun, melted at 196° . Ghosh states $190\text{--}191^\circ$ (with decomposition) as the *m. p.* of vasicine. The two substances obviously have *m. p.*'s quite close to each other, but a mixture of the two melts indefinitely from 160° upwards. We prepared a picrate of our synthetic base but the *m. p.* was 184° whilst that of the natural base is 199° . Clearly therefore the two substances are not identical.

Next we prepared the isopropyl analogue starting from isobutyranilide but the base obtained in this case melted at 227° . A mixture with the natural base melted indefinitely from 175° . The *m. p.* of the picrate of our synthetic base is $215\text{--}216^\circ$ and its mixture with that from natural base melted indefinitely. Therefore we are inclined to think that the structure advanced by Ghosh (*loc. cit.*) for vasicine is not the correct representation of its constitution.

For the purpose of these comparisons we obtained the crude vasicine from Dehra Dun but we had to take recourse to an elaborate scheme of purification (detailed in the experimental part). The melting point now recorded of the base is higher than that quoted by Sen and Ghosh. The purified base is almost odourless.

EXPERIMENTAL.

Purification of Crude Vasicine (from natural sources).

About 8 g. of the crude base is refluxed for about an hour with 50 c.c. of pure dry benzene. The extract is cooled and filtered. A

considerable quantity of resinous material is left undissolved. To the solution is added just sufficient ether to cause a slight turbidity when a further quantity of impure material comes down. This is removed and the solution is then diluted with more ether and is left to crystallise. The sides of the vessel are scratched from time to time and the vasicine crystallises out. This is collected and thrice crystallised from boiling alcohol with the aid of charcoal, m. p. 196° with decomposition. The crystals have a very pale buff colour but appear perfectly colourless in contact with the solvent. The substance is very sparingly soluble in alcohol in the pure state. The base dissolves in cold sulphuric acid without a colour, a drop of nitric acid imparts a yellow colour to the solution which, however, is discharged on dilution. The substance, on being heated in a dry test tube, decomposes and a basic gas is evolved. This does not seem to be ammonia but is not unlike dimethylamine in many respects. This cannot be emphasised at this stage because the material we had at our disposal was really too small. But we hope to characterise this later and we believe that this will ultimately throw considerable light on the constitution of the alkaloid.

Butyranilide.—Butyric acid (1 mol.) and aniline (1 mol.) with a few drops of pyridine were refluxed for 3 hours when the reaction was complete. The product was poured in much water (cold) whereupon the anilide separated out in crystals. Crystallised from hot dilute alcohol, m. p. 92° (*cf.* Gerhard, *Annalen*, 1853, 87, 166) m. p. 90°). Yield 80 g. from 40 g. of butyric acid.

Condensation of Butyranilide and Urethane.—Butyranilide (20 g.) and urethane (16 g.) in xylene (50 c.c.) were refluxed very gently ($140-145^{\circ}$) for 4 hours with phosphoric oxide (15 g.). From the cooled product xylene was completely decanted off and the residue was dissolved in water cautiously. The solution freed from insoluble matter was cooled with ice and basified with dilute sodium hydroxide solution (cold). The thick white precipitate of the basic product is filtered and freed from alkaline mother-liquor. It is then dissolved in dilute hydrochloric acid and reprecipitated with alkali. The crude base thus obtained was then twice crystallised from boiling absolute alcohol (about 50 c.c.) with the aid of charcoal in long thin needles, m. p. 197° . Yield 20 g. (Found: C, 70.8; H, 6.5; N, 14.96. $C_{11}H_{14}ON_2$ requires C, 70.2; H, 6.4; N, 14.9 per cent.). A mixture of this substance with an equal amount of vasicine melts indefinitely from 160° .

Preparation of the Picrate.—The synthetic base (1 g.) in alcohol (20 c.c.) was heated for sometime on the water-bath with an alcoholic solution of picric acid (1 g. in 20 c.c.) under reflux. The cooled product deposited fine cubical crystals of the picrate. These were collected and recrystallised from alcohol; m. p. 184°. (Found: N, 16.2. $C_{11}H_{11}N_3O_8$ requires N, 16.8 per cent.)

Action of Methyl Iodide on the Synthetic Base.—The base (1 g.) in methyl alcohol (10 c.c.) and excess of methyl iodide were refluxed, as prescribed by Sen and Ghosh (*loc. cit.*) for vasicine methiodide, for 2 hours on the water-bath. The cooled mixture deposited, however, the original substance unchanged. Therefore the synthetic base does not form a methiodide under the same conditions as vasicine does.

isoButyranilide.—This substance was prepared following the conditions detailed under butyranilide. The product, however, was poured on to only a small amount of cold saturated brine. The substance crystallised out on standing and had m. p. 101°. (*Cf.* Norton, *Amer. Chem. J.*, 1885, 7, 117, who gives m. p. 102.5).

Condensation of isoButyranilide and Urethane: Formation of 2-isoPropyl-4-oxy quinazoline.—A mixture of isobutyranilide (15 g.), urethane (10 g.) xylene (40 c.c.) and phosphoric oxide (10 g.) was heated at 140° in an oil-bath for 5 hours. Xylene was decanted off from the reaction mixture at the end of the reaction. The residue was dissolved in water and filtered. The filtrate was strongly cooled and carefully basified with cold dilute sodium hydroxide solution. The precipitated basic material was redissolved in dilute hydrochloric acid and reprecipitated with dilute alkali solution. It was finally crystallised several times from absolute alcohol in which it is sparingly soluble as fine long needles, m. p. 227° (with decomposition). (Found: N, 15.3. $C_{11}H_{12}ON_2$ requires N, 14.9 per cent.). A mixture of this base with natural vasicine melted indefinitely from 175° to 200°.

Picrate of the Base.—This was prepared exactly as the corresponding compound from the *n*-propyl analogue. The picrate crystallises in short stout yellow prisms, m. p. 215-216°. (Found: N, 17.04. $C_{11}H_{11}N_3O_8$ requires N, 16.8 per cent.)

Action of Methyl Iodide on the Base.—Following the procedure adopted by Sen and Ghosh, we found, on similar treatment, our synthetical base to be unchanged.

The two synthetic bases did not show the colour reaction noted in the case of natural vasicine.

In conclusion, we wish to thank Prof. Sir P. C. Rây for his very kind interest in the work, and also we wish to place on record our gratitude to Dr. J. N. Sen and Mr. T. P. Ghosh for their courtesy in giving us a specimen of (crude) vasicine.

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P. S.—Since the above was in print our attention was drawn to the compound 4-oxy-2-propylquinazoline (I) by Bischer and Lang (*Ber.*, 1895, 28,287). These authors state its m.p. to be 205°, whilst ours melts at 167°. Its difference from natural vasicine should be an apriori argument against the structure (I) for the latter. The corresponding isopropyl compound described by Nimentowski (*J.pr. Chem.*, (2) 51, 569) melts at 234°. This seems to be identical with our product, the m.p. of which however was found to be 3° higher than that recorded by Nimentowski.

The identity of both these quinazoline derivatives with ours proves at the same time that cyclic amidines are really obtained by Sen and Rây's method.

